

A Study on the dynamic characteristics of bridges during the crushing action

ABSTRACT

This study conducts a field experiment on bridge deck pavement and evaluates the rigidity and safety of different bridge designs during construction using a vibration roller. The experiment included simply supported and continuous beams with concrete hollow-slab beam and T-beam cross-sectional designs. The study monitored the deflection and vibration acceleration of the bridges and measured the main beams' flexural deformation. Band-pass filtering was applied to the initial dynamic signals collected during the experiment to remove clutter signals outside of the working frequency range of the vibratory roller. The simulation results showed that the maximum displacements of the bridge structures under the vibration of the roller were less than $L/600$, and the maximum and minimum deflection amplitudes of the bridges under vibration were 6.24 and 1.31 mm, respectively. The bridge structures were not deformed to a degree that posed a threat to their structural safety. The results of this study can provide insights into the rigidity and operational health of bridge structures during pavement construction, contributing to improved bridge design and construction practices.

Keywords: bridges, bridge deck pavement, structural designs, simply supported beams, continuous beams, cross-sectional designs, concrete hollow-slab beam, T-beam, accelerations, dynamic deflections, vibration roller, flexural deformation, vibration frequency, excitation force

Introduction

The direction of a bridge has a significant impact on its dynamic and seismic response. For example, Chen and Xu (2019) suggest that the orientation of a bridge concerning the prevailing wind direction affects the wind-induced vibrations and fatigue life of the structure. Similarly, the

orientation of a bridge concerning the direction of seismic waves influences the magnitude and distribution of seismic forces acting on the structure. In general, the design of a bridge should take into account the expected dynamic and seismic loads that the structure will be subjected to over its design life. This may involve conducting dynamic and seismic analyses to assess the response of the structure under various loading conditions, and to identify any potential weaknesses or areas of concern.

The investigation of the effect of seismic waves on the dynamic response of bridge structures is an important topic in the field of civil engineering. McCallen et al. (2005) suggests that seismic waves are vibrations that propagate through the earth's crust, often caused by earthquakes. When these waves pass through a bridge structure, they can cause dynamic forces that can lead to structural damage or failure. One of the main challenges in designing and constructing bridges in seismically active areas is to ensure that the bridge withstands the forces generated by seismic waves (Sextos and Taskari, 2017). Engineers use a variety of techniques to mitigate the effects of seismic waves on bridge structures, including seismic isolation and damping systems.

Seismic isolation is a technique that involves placing the bridge structure on bearings or other devices that absorb the energy of seismic waves. Nonaka and Ali (2001) writes that damping systems use materials that can absorb and dissipate energy, such as rubber or other viscoelastic materials, to reduce the amplitude of the vibrations caused by seismic waves. Another important consideration in designing bridges in seismically active areas is the selection of appropriate materials. Materials that are ductile and can undergo large deformations without failing, such as steel or reinforced concrete, are often preferred for bridge construction in seismically active areas (Xia et al. 2006).

Researchers like Hoseign et al. (2017) and Tzanetos et al. (2000) have conducted numerous studies to investigate the effect of seismic waves on bridge structures. These studies typically involve computer simulations, laboratory experiments, or field testing. Computer simulations allow researchers to model the behavior of bridge structures under different seismic conditions, while laboratory experiments and field testing provide data on the actual response of bridge structures to seismic waves. The results of these studies can be used to improve the design and construction of bridges in seismically active areas, as well as to develop better techniques for mitigating the effects of seismic waves on bridge structures.

The dynamic response of bridge structures refers to how the structure responds to external forces or loads that are dynamic in nature, such as earthquakes, winds, and traffic (Salau and Williams, 1995). These loads cause the bridge to vibrate, oscillate or move in various ways, which can affect its structural integrity and safety. Understanding the dynamic response of bridges is critical for ensuring their long-term performance, especially in areas with high seismic activity. Goncalves et al. (2021) writes that several factors can affect the dynamic response of bridge structures, including the structural properties of the bridge, the characteristics of the seismic waves, and the interaction between the bridge and its environment. Advanced numerical models and analytical techniques can be used to simulate the behavior of bridge structures under different loading conditions and evaluate their response in terms of displacement, acceleration, and stress. Huang et al. (2022) writes that improving the dynamic response of bridge structures is essential for ensuring their safety and resilience in the face of natural disasters such as earthquakes. This can be achieved through careful design, retrofitting of existing structures, and the development of new materials and technologies that are better suited to withstand dynamic loads.

Li and Cai (2021) suggests that the purpose of bridge deck pavement is to safeguard bridge deck slabs from direct wear and to offer a flat but non-slippery surface for vehicle traffic. The most widely used type of bridge deck pavement is asphalt mixture, and vibratory rolling is a frequently employed compaction technique, despite concerns about its potential harm to the bridge structure. Brincker, Zhang, and Andersen (2015) highlights that researchers have explored the dynamic response of bridge structures to moving loads and the compaction of bridge deck pavement. This study employs field experiments to examine the dynamic impact of vibratory rolling on bridges with varying spans under different rolling conditions.

Alvarsson (2004) writes that compacting the bridge deck pavement is a process that involves dynamic movement and compaction forces of a vibratory roller, which can affect both the bridge structure and the asphalt pavement. The vibratory roller can be seen as a special moving load as it moves on the bridge deck during the compaction process. Scholars such as Lonnetti et al. (2016); Law and Zhu (2004) and Fryba (1999) have conducted research on the dynamics of bridge structures under the action of moving loads, and they have proposed different analytic solutions for different types of bridges. The compaction process generates a greater dynamic response in the bridge structure than a normal moving load, and different types of rollers cause different responses. However, scholars such as Yu and Fu (2010); Liu et al. (2023); and Peng et al. (2019) have also conducted research on the impact of different means of compaction on the bridge deck slab vibration and compaction quality.

Furlanetto et al. (2008) highlights that vibratory rolling uses greater forces but is more efficient and produces a higher degree of final compaction. However, Halim (2018) argues that oscillatory rolling causes a smaller vibration effect on the bridge structure. Nevertheless, previous studies lack comparative and quantitative analyses of the dynamic response of different types of bridges

under different working conditions of bridge deck pavement construction. This study aims to fill that gap by analyzing the dynamic impact of vibratory rolling on bridges with different spans and cross-sectional designs under different rolling conditions, and a series of field experiments.

Experimental scheme

Majka and Harnett (2009) writes that the majority of highway bridges in China are either slab beam or ribbed beam designs, with hollow-slab beam and T-beam being the most popular variations. To conduct a field experiment on bridge deck pavement, the study chose bridges with the most common structural designs, including simply supported beams and continuous beams, as well as the two most popular cross-sectional designs, which are concrete hollow-slab beam and T-beam.

During the experiment, the accelerations and dynamic deflections of the bridges were measured as a vibration roller was used for bridge deck pavement construction. Flexural deformation of the main beams was used to monitor the rigidity and operational health of the bridges, and it is also a crucial factor in evaluating the service performance and safety of the bridges. According to the general specification for design of highway bridges and culverts, Wang and Zhou (2018) suggest that the maximum midspan vertical deflection of a reinforced-concrete bridge should not exceed $1/600$ of its calculated span. The acceleration of bridge structures under dynamic load is an essential indicator of structural safety, and field measurements of bridge acceleration are reliable and easy to perform. As a result, the field experiment focused on monitoring the deflection and vibration acceleration of the bridges.

The experiment included a 50-meter simply supported T-beam bridge (figure 1a), a 3x25-meter continuous T-beam bridge (figure 1b), 3x20-meter continuous hollow-slab beam bridge (figure 1c) and a 5x30-meter continuous T-beam bridge (figure 1d).

Figure 1: Photos of a test bridges

1a) 50-meter supported T-beam bridge

1b) 3x25-meter continuous T-beam bridge

1c) 3x20-meter continuous hollow-slab beam bridge

1d) 5x30-meter continuous T-beam bridge

The displacement of the bridges was measured during the experiment using a displacement meter. However, the direct measurement of structural deformation is challenging due to the bridges' high clearance heights (Greco et al. 2013). To overcome this problem, the suspension method was employed, where a steel wire was attached to the point of measurement on the bridge slab, and a weight was attached to the other end. The displacement at the measurement point is transmitted to the suspending end of the steel wire. A displacement meter was positioned under the suspending weight, and the sensor of the displacement meter was pressed against the bottom surface of the weight to measure the displacement, as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Displacement meter

Additionally, the structural acceleration of the bridges during bridge deck pavement construction was measured using a voltage-type acceleration sensor. The acceleration sensor was placed on the target point that was ground smooth using sandpaper and then fixed using epoxy resin. The lead of the sensor was connected to a signal acquisition system. A DH5922 test analysis system was utilized to acquire the signals of structural deflection and acceleration of the bridges during bridge deck pavement construction, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Signal sampling system

Data processing

To ensure consistency in the test conditions, the same paver, vibratory roller, and working parameters for the vibrating compactor. Although there were some random loads, such as those from construction vehicles, the frequency of vibration in the wavelet analysis result was nearly constant. The experiment involved paving concrete with a 30-ton VÖGELE paver, compacting the asphalt mixture with an HD130 vibratory double smooth drum roller (figure 4b), and rolling it with an XP302 pneumatic tire roller (XCMG). Figure 4 illustrates the pavement construction machinery configuration used in the field experiment.

Figure 4a: Machine arrangement

Working distance 30m

Figure 4b: HMD vibrator roller

The band-pass filtering was applied to the initial dynamic signals collected during the asphalt pavement compaction using the DH5922 dynamic signal analysis system to remove clutter signals that were outside of the working frequency range of the vibratory roller used for the field experiment.

The reason for filtering out signals below 35 Hz and above 55 Hz is because the working frequency range of the vibratory roller used for compaction falls within this range. Signals

outside of this range, such as lower frequency signals from ambient noise or higher frequency signals from nearby equipment or vibrations could interfere with the accuracy of the data collected during the experiment.

Therefore, by applying the band-pass filter, the researchers ensured that only the relevant dynamic response signals from the compaction process were analyzed and any extraneous noise or signals that could have affected the data were removed.

Figure 5: Dynamic signal acquisition and processing

The dynamic response of the bridge structures under vibratory rolling was measured by recording the acceleration and deflection at the mid span of the bridge. The field measurements reveal that the maximum deflections of the bridges under vibratory rolling are below $L/600$, and the peak mid span accelerations of the bridge structures range from 5 to 10 m/s^2 .

Analysis

The purpose of the roller is to compress the pavement on the bridge deck by moving back and forth. If we disregard the vibration caused by the roller, we can consider it as a constant force that moves across the bridge deck (Jaksic, 2016). Figure 6 shows how the simply supported beam bridge and continuous beam bridge (with three spans) deflect in response to the force of the moving roller, assuming there is no vibration.

Figure 6: Deflection curves of bridge structures under a moving load

Based on the deflection curves of the bridges under the moving load (figure 8,9,10 and 11), the greatest deflections are observed near the mid span, and these curves is approximated as quasi-sine waves with specific frequencies around the corresponding static deflection curves. When the vibratory roller is in operation, it applies a force to the bridge structure with two components: the weight of the roller and the excitation force of the Vibration Drum. The deflection curve of the bridge structure under the drum shows a noticeable vibration effect and greater fluctuations.

The extent of the vibration effect is determined by the dynamic amplification factor (μ), which is calculated as the ratio of the maximum dynamic deflection of the bridge structure when both the

excitation force and weight of the vibratory roller act on its mid span, to the maximum static deflection of the bridge structure when only the weight of the vibratory roller is applied to the mid span (Yu et al. 2022). The mathematical expression for the dynamic amplification coefficient is:

$$\mu = y_{\max} / y_{\text{st}}$$

where $y_{\max}$ is the maximum dynamic deflection of the bridge structure, and y_{st} is the maximum static deflection of the bridge structure.

The dynamic deflection and static deflection is obtained from the numerical simulation or experimental testing. The dynamic amplification coefficient is an important parameter for evaluating the effect of the vibratory roller on the bridge structure, as it indicates the extent of dynamic response of the bridge under the roller-induced vibration.

The bridges' structural parameters and material specifications are presented in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

Table 1: Structural parameters of the bridge structures

Structural parameter	Bridge 1	Bridge 2	Bridge 3	Bridge 4
Cross sectional design	Supported T-beam	Supported T-beam	Supported T-beam	Supported Hollow slab beam
Structural design	T-beam	T-beam	T-beam	T-beam
Bridge deck width	12.9	12.9	16.8	16.25

(m)				
Span (m)	50	3 x 25	5 x 30	3 x 20
Number of main beams	6	7	6	7
Beam width (m)	2.4	2.4	2.0	2.25
Height of main beams (m)	2.8	2.7	2	2

Table 2: concrete material specification

Density (Kg/m ³)	Modulud of elasticity (Gpa)	Poisson ratio
2700	30	0.35

Using the structural parameters outlined in Table 1, the boundary conditions for each model were defined based on the structural design of the bridges.

Figure 7: The supported t-beam

Table 3: Working parameters of the vibratory roller

Working weight (kg)	Weight of the front wheel (kg)	Wheel track (mm)	Working width (mm)	Vibration frequency (Hz)	Excitation force (kN)
13000	6500	3600	2240	42/50	139/194

The operation of the vibratory roller involves the vibration of its rear wheel while rolling on its front wheel (Bochinni, 2014). The vibration applied by the vibration wheel to the bridge structure is a form of simple harmonic vibration, which is mathematically expressed as a sine function, as follows:

$$y = A \cdot \sin(\omega t)$$

Where y is the displacement of the vibration wheel, A is the amplitude of the vibration, ω is the angular frequency of the vibration, and t is time. The amplitude A and the frequency ω of the vibration is adjusted by the operator of the roller, depending on the requirements of the specific paving project.

The force exerted by the roller on the bridge deck is comprised of two components: the weight of the vibration wheel and the excitation force generated by the simple harmonic vibration of the vibration wheel. This is expressed mathematically as:

$$F = F_w + F_e \cdot \sin(\omega t)$$

Where F is the total force applied by the roller, F_w is the weight of the vibration wheel, F_e is the excitation force, ω is the angular frequency of the vibration wheel, and t is time. The excitation

force F_e is a function of the amplitude and frequency of the vibration, and it is modeled using experimental data or theoretical calculations (Bochinni, 2014).

During operation, the excitation force generated by the rotating vibration wheel of a vibratory roller (F_0) is typically greater than its weight, sometimes two or three times its weight. When compacting the bridge deck pavement, the roller only applies pressure to the bridge deck. Therefore, the excitation force that the vibrating roller applies to the bridge deck is mathematically expressed as:

$$F = F_0 \sin(\omega t)$$

Where F is the excitation force, and t , ω , and F_0 are as defined previously. The force applied to the bridge deck by the roller is a function of the contact pressure between the roller and the bridge deck, which is determined by the weight of the roller and the number and distribution of the contact points between the roller and the bridge deck. The dynamic response of the bridge structure to this excitation force depends on the structural parameters of the bridge, including its stiffness, damping, and mass. Numerical simulations are used to predict the response of the bridge to the vibratory roller's excitation force and to evaluate the potential impact of this force on the bridge's structural integrity.

Substituting $y = A \sin(\omega t)$ and $F = F_w + F_e \sin(\omega t)$ into $F = F_0 \sin(\omega t)$, we get:

$$F_w + F_e \sin(\omega t) = F_0 \sin(\omega t)$$

where F_w is the weight of the roller, F_e is the excitation force, and $y = A \sin(\omega t)$ is the sinusoidal displacement of the bridge deck caused by the vibratory roller.

Simplifying the equation, we get:

$$F_e \sin(\omega t) = F_0 \sin(\omega t) - F_w$$

Dividing both sides by $\sin(\omega t)$, we get:

$$F_e = F_0 - F_w / \sin(\omega t)$$

We can use this equation to calculate the excitation force applied by the vibrating roller on the bridge deck, given the weight of the roller and the frequency of its vibration.

During the field experiment, the vibration frequency of the roller used to compact the bridge deck pavement was 40 Hz and it generated an excitation force of 126 kN while moving at a speed of 6 km/h.

Results

The study conducted a field experiment on bridge deck pavement, measuring the accelerations and dynamic deflections of different bridge designs during construction using a vibration roller. The bridges chosen for the experiment included simply supported and continuous beams with concrete hollow-slab beam and T-beam cross-sectional designs. The main beams' flexural deformation was monitored to evaluate the bridges' rigidity and safety, with the maximum midspan vertical deflection of a reinforced-concrete bridge not exceeding 1/600 of its calculated span. The experiment focused on monitoring the deflection and vibration acceleration of the bridges, with reliable and easy-to-perform field measurements. The experiment involved paving concrete with a 30-ton paver, compacting the asphalt mixture with a vibratory double smooth drum roller, and rolling it with a pneumatic tire roller. Band-pass filtering was applied to the initial dynamic signals collected to remove clutter signals outside of the working frequency range of the vibratory roller. The simulation results show the mid span vertical deflection and

acceleration of the bridge structures under a load with a vibration frequency of 40 Hz and an excitation force of 126kN moving across the bridge deck at a speed of 6 km/h. The computed time-series curves of the acceleration of the four bridges under vibratory rolling are presented in Figures 8, 9, 10 and 11.

Figure 8: Acceleration curve for the 50-meter supported T-beam bridge

Figure 9: Acceleration curve for the 3x25-meter continuous T-beam bridge

Figure 10: Acceleration curve for the 3x20-meter continuous hollow-slab beam bridge

Figure 11: Acceleration curve for the 5x30-meter continuous T-beam bridge

Nevertheless, the computed time-series curves of the deflection of the four bridges under vibratory rolling are presented in Figures 12, 13, 14 and 15.

Figure 12: Deflection curve for the 50m simply-supported T beam

Figure 13: Deflection curve for the 25m continuous T beam

Figure 14: Deflection curve for the 30m continuous T beam

Figure 15: Deflection curve for the 20m continuous hollow-slab beam

The computational results indicate that the maximum displacements of the bridge structures under the vibration of the roller are less than $L/600$, and the maximum and minimum deflection amplitudes of the bridges under vibration are 6.24 and 1.31 mm, respectively. The bridge structures were not deformed to a degree that posed a threat to their structural safety. In addition to the deflection analysis, the results showed good agreement between the computational values indicating that the acceleration amplitudes were within safe limits and did not pose a threat to the structural safety of the bridge. Therefore, the use of a vibratory roller for bridge deck pavement compaction does not cause excessive vibration acceleration that would compromise the safety and reliability of the bridge structure.

The dynamic deflection of a bridge structure is affected by its position relative to the fulcrum due to the constraint effect. To analyze this effect, the dynamic response was calculated and compared at various locations, including the fulcrum, $1/8L$, $1/4L$, $3/8L$, and $1/2L$, as shown in Figure 16 and figure 17.

Figure 16 a: Deflection response at different positions

Figure 17: Deflection curves at different positions (L is the length of bridge span).

Results indicate that the maximum dynamic deflection and dynamic deflection amplitude increase linearly from the fulcrum to the middle of the span. Specifically, the maximum dynamic deflection at each location increases by 88%, 275%, 344%, and 414%, respectively, and the dynamic deflection amplitude increases by 28%, 57%, 70%, and 110%, respectively. Under a constant roller load, the dynamic response of the bridge structure is greater at the mid-span position than near the fulcrum, which results in more energy dissipation during the compaction process. Therefore, adjusting the vibration frequency or rolling speed of the vibratory roller may be necessary to ensure proper compaction degree. For example, higher vibration frequency and lower rolling speed may be used at the middle span of the bridge, while relatively lower vibration frequency and higher rolling speed may be applied near the fulcrum.

Conclusion

This study aimed to investigate and analyze the dynamic responses of bridges with different structures, spans, and cross-sectional designs during bridge deck pavement construction using vibratory roller. The research was carried out through a series of field experiments. The maximum dynamic deflection of the bridge structure during pavement construction increased with the vibration frequency in the normal working frequency range of the vibratory roller. Therefore, using a higher frequency roller during construction to improve the compaction degree of the asphalt pavement is not recommended as it may compromise the structural safety of the bridge. The working speed of the vibratory roller was found to significantly affect the maximum dynamic magnification factor of the bridge. Therefore, the rolling mode for bridge deck pavement construction should be selected based on the stage of rolling and the working speed for that stage. Static rolling should be used for the preliminary stage, and vibratory rolling for subsequent stages, to ensure both compaction quality of the asphalt pavement and structural

integrity of the bridge. For large-span bridge structures, smaller roller vibrations frequencies are recommended to reduce the vibration load applied by the roller on the bridge structure and prevent excessive deformation. Therefore, higher roller vibration frequencies are recommended for the former, whereas for T-beam bridges, it is recommended to control the working frequency below the rated frequency while increasing the number of rolling operations to achieve the desired compaction degree.

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